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ART. II.—*Khadāvadā Inscription of Gyâsa Sahi.*

[*Vikrama*] *Samvat* 1541.

By D. R. BHANDARKAR, M.A., *Poona.*

(*Communicated.*)

This inscription, which is published for the first time, was discovered by Major Dube, when Chief Gazetteer Officer, Indore Durbar, on a well at Khaḍāvadā in the district of Rāmpurā in the Indore territory. The stone bearing the inscription was lying in his house in 1905, and it is from the paper-impressions kindly supplied by him that the following transcript is prepared.

The writing, to judge from the impressions, covers a space of about 4'-9" broad by 1'-10" high and is in a state of fair preservation throughout. The characters are *devanagari* of the 15th century. The language is Sanskrit; and with the exception of the opening salutation to Gaṇeśa and Bhārati and the concluding benediction to the scribe and the reciter, the entire inscription is in verse. The fault of *vatibhaṅga* or break of cæsura frequently occurs in this poetic composition, and solecisms, though few, are not altogether absent. Verses 51-54 are characterised by *yamaka* or repetition of letters of the same sound at the end of two consecutive *pādis*. In respect of orthography, we have to notice (1) the substitution of *chchha* for *stha* in *chchhīrībhava*° in l. 14, in °*ichchhāna* in ll. 15-16, and so forth. (2) the disregard of the rule of *sandhi* in the case of *t* and *ś*, e.g., in *vahat-śālmali*° in l. 16, (3) the use of *v* for *b* only twice, in verses 63 and 64, and (4) the splitting up of conjunct consonants into two separate letters, in *dolayan-tyātmiyam* l. 21, °*paris-khala*° l. 22, and so forth. As regards lexicography, it is to be remarked that the poet is very fond of using rare or obscure words; e.g., no less than three such words occur in l. 22, *vis. khidga, chamātaka* and *laṅgura*.

After the adoration and invocation of deities as usual, the composer of the inscription describes, in magniloquent terms in verses 5-6, the glory and prosperity of the country of Mālava (Mālwā), where both Śiva and Kārttikeya, leaving the Himālayas, had, we are told, fixed their abode. In this country there was triumphant (v. 7) at the city of Māṇḍavya on the Vindhya mountains a king of the name of Hūsaṅga, a Gorī, a gem of the Yavana race, and the sun to the lotuses, *vis.*, the Śaka tribe. The king mentioned is undoubtedly Hūshang (Alp Khān) Ghūrī, the second Sultan of Mālwā, who first made Māṇḍū (Māṇḍavya) his capital. In verse 8 Māṇḍū is compared to the capital town of Indra, and, in the verse following, nothing but

conventional praise has been bestowed upon Sultan Hūshang. The next verse (10), if we carefully notice the *double entendre* obviously intended, informs us that Hūshang secured a number of elephants from the Vindhya mountains, after making friends with Naganātha. Historians assert that Hūshang went disguised as a horse-dealer to Jājnagar (Jājpur) in Cuttack in Orissa to barter his horses for the war-elephants of the Rājā of Jājnagar, and was successful in securing 150 elephants there to fight against the Sultan of Gujarāt with whom he was at war. Naganātha may, therefore, be reasonably supposed to be no other person than the prince of Jājnagar himself. Verse 11 describes his defeat of the king of Kālapriyāpattana, Kādīrasāhi by name, who ceded his son, daughter and ministers to Hūshang. They all repaired to the city of Maṇḍapa (Māṇḍû), and the most pre-eminent of them all was Khāna Salaha (v. 12) who became an object of confidence with Hūshang. Kālapriyāpattana must undoubtedly be Kālpi¹ in Bundelkhaṇḍ, and Kādīrasāhi, Abdul Kādūr, a Delhi officer in charge of this fortress, which the Ferishta represents Hūshang to have reduced, but which after receiving homage was delivered back by him to Abdul Kādūr. In the verse following (13), we are told that Salaha was originally a minister of Kādīra Sāhi, and was, owing to his fitness, appointed to the same post by Hūshang who made him a Khān, and entirely left the work of administration to him. Verse 14 says that after the death of Hūshang, the throne was seized by Mahamūdā, the sun to the water-lily, *viz.*, the Khilchī family. Muḥammad (Ghazni Khān), son of Hūshang, is thus passed over, and the name of the usurper Māḥmūd Shāh I. Khālji, mentioned in the inscription. The next verse describes the latter's conquests. He desolated Dhillī (Dehli), harassed the Chola king, subjugated the province of Utkala (Orissa), and vanquished the Draviḍa king. Verse 16 refers to the implicit confidence reposed by Māḥmūd in Salaha, who destroyed (v. 17) eighty elephants of the Sultan of Gujarāt who had assailed with his army the Sultan of Mālwā. The Sultan of Gujarāt here referred to must be Muzaffar I. The next verse informs us that Gayāsa succeeded Māḥmūd to the throne. Gayāsa, or Gyāsa as he is called further on, is unquestionably Ghīyās Shūh Khālji. Verses 19-20 are a pure eulogy of Gyāsa Sāhi, the ornament of the Pārasika race. In the verse following, we are told that Salaha was allowed to retain his post by Ghīyās also. Verse 22 contains nothing but conventional praise of Salaha, but, from the next verse, we glean that, on hearing of a rebellion raised by Śabarās, Salaha appointed Baharī, who was regarded as son from his birth by

¹ I am indebted to Munshi Deviprasādji of Jodhpur for this identification.

the former, to quell the revolt. Verse 24 describes the defeat inflicted by Baharī on the Śabara kings at the city of Kḥiḍāvada on the bank of the Charmanvatī (Chambal). Kḥiḍāvada is unquestionably Khaḍāvada, where the inscription was found. Verse 25 gives no historical information, but the verse following tells us that Baharī, lord of Pārasikas, vanquished a king named Kshemakarna at Śamkhoddhāra between the two banks of the river raised by Rantideva, i.e., the Chambal. Verse 27 also contains the historical information that Baharī extracted the dart, viz., Ivarāhima, which was rankling in the breast of the Sultan of Mālava. But who this Ivarāhima or Ibrāhim was, is unknown to me. The next three verses set forth the munificent nature of Baharī, and from verse 31 we learn that Baharī, leader of Śakas, excavated a tank in the town of Śālmāmat. From the next verse we gather that to the north of this tank he had dug another tank, which was thought to be a small milky ocean. The verse following tells us that he constructed another tank to the north of this. Verses 34-35 describe the tanks and the many advantages conferred thereby on the passers-by. In verse 36 we are informed that in Kḥiḍāvada to the south of that city he constructed a spacious step-well, to a poetic description of which the *praśastikāra* has devoted the next eight verses. Verse 45 further informs us that, above and surrounding the well, he raised a nice attractive orchard, which is also described at length in no less than ten verses. Verse 56 pronounces the wish that Baharī, his sons and grandsons, be spared together with the well as long as the Meru, the sun, and so forth endure. In verses 57-62 the poet sets forth his own genealogy. In the lineage of Bhṛigu, we are told, there was Śrī-Somanātha who performed the sacrificial rites of the spring season every year; his son was Narahari, who was an expert in logic, and who, being a reciter of the Vedas appropriately bore the *biruda* of *ilā-tala-virañchi*, i.e., "the god Brahmā on the surface of the earth." From Narahari sprang Śrī-Keśava, who was also known as Jhoṅga. His son was Atri, who was conversant with *vedānta*, *mīmāṃsā*, and rhetoric, who was the leader of the Daśapura Brāhmaṇa caste, and who was held in respect by the Guhila king Kumbha. His son was Śrī-Maheśa, lord of poets, proficient in *darśanas* and an able dilectician. He lived as poet in Mālava for some time, and it was he who composed the *praśasti* engraved on the well of Baharī. All these verses (57-62) except the last, descriptive of the genealogy of Maheśa, the composer of our *praśasti*, occur with slight changes in an inscription in the celebrated temple of Eklingjī, 14 miles north of Udaipur, Mewār. This record which is dated in V. E. 1545 and is consequently posterior to our

inscription by four years, was also composed by Maheśa, who then, as he himself tells us therein, was a poet in the assembly of the Guhila sovereign Rājamalla. Maheśa's father Atri, as we have seen, was honoured by Kumbhakarṇa. We are not informed whether he was his *protégé*. Probably he was. But though it is not certain that Maheśa's father flourished in the court of a Guhila prince, there can be no doubt that Maheśa was, and that he was the recipient of the patronage of Kumbhakarṇa's son, Rājamalla. This patronage he enjoyed till at least V. E. 1556, the date of the inscription found at Ghosūṇḍī, which was composed by Maheśa himself, and which records the construction of a step-well by Śrīṅgāṇa-devī, queen of Rājamalla.

From verse 63 we learn that the work of excavating the well was completed on Thursday, the *Dharma-tithi* of the bright half of Kārtika, in Vikrama Samvat 1541, during the Paridhāvin cyclic year. *Dharma-tithi* is the second *tithi* of the bright half of Kārtika, also called *Yama-tithi*, or, in Marāṭhī, *Dharmarājīcht bij*. The date, as kindly calculated for me by the late Prof. Kielhorn, regularly corresponds to Thursday, the 21st October A.D. 1484. The learned Doctor further informed me that this day fell in the year Paridhāvin, which commenced 17 hours 1 minute after mean sunrise of the 28th June A.D. 1484 and that here we had a good instance of the strict mean-sign system (*Ind. Ant.* Vol. XX, p. 411).

Verses 64-67 give us interesting information about the genealogy of Śalaha. In Hamīrpura there was a king called Śrī-Bhairava, who was the son of the Karachulli family. Hamīrpura is doubtless the same as Hamīrapurā, the principal town of the district of the same name, now comprised in the United Provinces. Karachulli, again, appears to be the same as Kalachuri, whose rule was supreme in Central Provinces. Of King Bhairava there was one Sumedhas, who was the best *Mādhyamīna* Brāhmaṇa, and who was attached to two Vedas. From Sumedhas sprang Arthapati, who elevated his Bhārgava *gotra* by his merits. His son was Purushottama, a devotee of Śiva, and his son was Ghuḍaū, who was made a *pārasika*, i.e., a Muhammadan, by Kādīra Śāhi. After becoming a *yavana*, Ghuḍaū assumed the name Śalaha and was made a khān by Mahamūda, i.e., Maḥmud Shāh I. In verse 68 is contained the other interesting fact that Śalaha made Baharī a *yavana*, who was originally a *Kshatriya*. The last verse (69), as might naturally be expected, tells us that the mason who constructed the well was Kshetrasiṃha, son of Jhāmjhā.

TEXT¹.

- 1.—स्वस्ति श्रीगणेशभारताभ्यान्नमः ॥ आनंदोसुंगतनवे विशुद्धज्ञानमानवे ॥^१ विश्वप्र-
काशिने तस्मै नमः कस्मैचिदस्तु नः ॥ १ ॥ उदित्वरदिवाकरद्युतिसपत्नरत्नप्र-
भाविभासितमभीप्सितं दिशतु बोर्धवामं वपुः ॥ हरस्य हरिणेक्षणीभवनदशिताम—
- 2.—त्सरस्मरस्मरणमिदुमत्कचन विदुमत् कुत्रचित् ॥ २ ॥^२ रणच्चरणधर्षरीविततताल-
सङ्गल्लरीपरीतसुरजस्वनोनुगततांडवाडंबरः ॥^३ प्रपोथयतु मन्मथं प्रतिरथांगभूर्भौ-
वुकप्रभूतपरिपंथिनः प्रचयवारिवाचां^४ पथि ॥ ३ ॥ पुरारिपुरसुंदरीचिकुरविस्फुर-
न्मंजरीपरागपरिपिंजरीकृतमगेन्द्रकन्ये तव ॥ भजामि चरणद्वयं कृतसरोजगर्वव्ययं
प्रपंचय वच^५ स्वयं झटिति
- 3.—वाणि कल्याणि मे ॥४४॥ जयत्यवनिमंडनं जनपदः पदं संपदां स मालवसमाह्वयः
पदम (?) मास यत्रादधौ ॥ शिवः शरवणोद्भवः सदनमुच्चकैश्चात्मनश्चकार रज-
ताचलं परिहरन् गुणांभोनिधौ ॥ ५ ॥ ग्रामे ग्रामे चित्रसत्रैः पवित्रैर्वीतत्रासाः
संसृतेर्यत्र संतः ॥ लोकाः कोकामित्रमित्राननानामंतस्तोषं विभ्रमैर्बिभ्रति
- 4.—स्मा॥६॥ असुप्मिन् दुर्वारप्रतिरथपुरंध्रीपरीचितप्रतापश्रीगौरौ यवनकुलरत्नं व्यजयता॥
गिरौ विध्येबंध्यद्रुममहिममांडव्यनगरे हुसंगक्षोणीद्रः शकनिकरपंकेरुहरविः ॥ ७ ॥
यन्मंदाकिनयंति निहंरसरित्रीराणि यन्नंदनं मुद्यत्केलिवनानि कल्पतरवंतीभ्याश्च
दंभद्विषः ॥ यच्चास्मिन् सुरकोविदंति कवयो नाना—
- 5.—कलाहंयवस्तन्मांडव्यपुरं पुरंदरपुरः पर्यायतां [नांचतु] ॥ ८ ॥ हुसंगक्षोणीद्रे
कलितकरवाले विदधिरे न धीराः संचारं विमतमतयः संगरभुवि ॥ स्फुटं पाणी
तेषामनुचरिकृतः के स्म मुकुलं दलत्कोशौ दंतास्तृणभरमनैष्टामपि भयात् ॥ ९ ॥
विध्याचलानुहुरुगजव्रजमाजहार कृत्वा हुसंगनृपतिनेगनाथमाप्यं ॥ प्रत्य—
- 6.—धिवीरवरसंगररोधहेतो^६ सेतोः कृताबिष गिरिव्रजमांजनेयः ॥ १० ॥ काले दिग्वि-
जयोद्यतः परपुरप्राकारभंगोलसदोर्धर्षः कचिदभ्यषेणयदयं कालप्रियापत्तनं ॥ व्रस्तः
कादिरसाहिरस्य नृपतिस्तस्मादुपाजीहरत्तत्सुनूं निजकन्यकां सह महामाथ्यैः
कियाद्भिर्विभुं ॥ ११ ॥ सर्वेमी सुधियो गुणैरनणुभिश्चित्ते निजस्वामिनस्तोषं
तेनुरदोपमेत्य नगरं श्रीमंडपख्याति—
- 7.—मत् ॥ अग्रण्यः समभूदमीषु समदप्रत्यर्थिदपोपहः खानश्रासलहा हुसंगयवनाधी-
शस्य विश्वासभूः ॥ १२ ॥ पूर्वं कादिरसाहिभूमिरमणः साचिव्यमत्रादधावौचित्येन

¹ From ink-impressions.

² Read "सङ्गल्लरी."

The reading of this letter is doubtful.

³ The reading of the first four letters is not certain.

⁴ Read वचः

⁵ The reading "सप" for "रोष" is not impossible.

- दुसंगसाहिरपि च प्रायुक्तं कृत्येषु तं ॥ एनं खानपदेभिषिच्य भुजयोरेतस्य भूत्वा
 भरं भूमेः शर्म स नर्मजातमभजङ्गपः कियद्वत्सरं ॥ १३ ॥ दुसंगक्षोणीशेनुस-
- 8.—रति यशःशेषसरणिं धरां धाराधारामधृत महमूदक्षितिपतिः ॥ प्रजा यस्मिन् खिल्वी-
 कुलकमलभानौ प्रभवति प्रभूतार्थानर्थध्वनितमधृतार्थं व्यष्टणुत ॥ १४ ॥ विह्रीमुन्नाद-
 शिल्लीमुखरतरुचरद्वल्लिपलीमुदंचच्चोलं वित्रासलोलं विघटनविवशानुत्कलानां प्रदे-
 शान् ॥ चक्रं चक्रेतिरौद्रद्रविडपरिवृढस्यापि दिग्जैत्र-
- 9.—यात्रारंभभ्रंगमात्रादमहिममहमूदक्षिताद्रो विनिद्रं ॥ १५ ॥ असौ भुवो भारमुदार-
 चित्ते निधाय खाने सलहाभिधाने ॥ न किं ददौ कन्न जिगाय किन्न जहौ न भोग्यं
 कतमद्भुभोज ॥ १६ ॥ मालवमभिषेणयतो गूर्जरनृपतेरशीतिमातंगान् ॥ संगरगिरि-
 वरचारी जधान सलहाह्मकेसरी कुपितः ॥ १७ ॥ संप्राप्य मानुषजनपुः फलमप्यशेष-
- 10.—मंतर्दधे स महमूदमहीमहेंद्रः ॥ राज्यं गयासन्पमात्मजमर्हणीयमानीय निजित-
 विपक्षमपेक्षणीयं ॥ १८ ॥ मांढव्यदुर्गमधितिष्ठति ग्यासभूपे न व्यासमापुररिभूमि-
 भृतो जगत्यां ॥ प्राच्याचले चलति चंडरुचावचंडाः किं कौशिकाः कचन
 कौशलमावहंति ॥ १९ ॥ दंडः केवलमातपत्रनिचये मुक्तासु वेधावधिर्बधः कंचुकसं-
- 11.—धिषु प्रतिबलं वाजिन्नत्रे चापलं ॥ उद्वाहे करपीडनं कुचयुगे काठिन्यमुन्नीयते
 भूमिं शासति पारसीकतिलके श्रीग्यासमाहिप्रभौ ॥ २० ॥ तातप्रेमारपदत्वाद्गुणगण-
 गरिमालंकृतत्वाद्ग्यासक्षोणीभृत्कृत्यजाते शलहमधिकृतेष्वभ्यधिचक्रप्रधानं ॥ कार्यं
 साफल्यमागात्समुचितमुररीकुर्वतानेननीरप्राचुर्यै-
- 12.—णाभिष्टुद्धं वनमिव सहसा संभृतं दोहदेन ॥ २१ ॥ आकर्णाकृष्टचापच्युतश नि-
 करोन्निन्नवक्षोविपक्षक्षोणीभृद्भूरिकक्षक्षतत्रपरिलसत्संगरोवासिररसु ॥ धावद्दारालघात-
 प्रपतदरिशिरास्यंजनांभोजशोभामाविःकुर्यति यत् श्रीशलहनरपतेर्युद्धवैदग्ध्यमेतत् ॥
 २२ ॥ गयासक्षोणींद्रप्रतिनिधिरथोन्नीय शबरप्रभृतं वा-
- 13.—यव्यां दिशि जनपदत्रासमनिशं ॥ सुतप्रायं बाल्यानृपचरितमध्याप्य बहरी
 महावीरं वैरिप्रशमविधेयोजयदयं ॥ २३ ॥ स्वामित्वं धरणेनिजेशवचनादासादय-
 न्नुद्धुरं दुर्गं दुर्गमचीकरत्स बहरी सधोधविष्ठाधरं ॥ प्राच्यां चारुखिडावदाह्वयपुरे
 चर्मन्वतीतीरके^३ वामं पादमिव प्रतापिशबरक्षोणीभुजां मूर्द्धनि ॥ २४ ॥ बहरी
 सृगेंद्र इव
- 14.—कंदरं गिरेनिजदुर्गमाप्य रिपुकुंजरव्रजं ॥ शरशक्तिकुंतनखरेर्व्यर्दादरनिशितैरिवाश-
 निभिरद्रिमद्रिभित् ॥ २५ ॥ शंखोद्दारे रंतिदेवोद्धृतायाः स्रोतस्विन्यास्तीरमप्येभ्य-

Read "जनुःफल"

Read यच्छ्री.

Read चर्मन्वती.

भावि ॥ खजाखज्जि क्षेमकर्णक्षितीशचान्वत् (?) बहरीपारसीकेश्वरेण ॥ २६ ॥
इवराहिमाह्वयमुरच्छिरीभवद्गुरुमालवावनिपतेररुंतुदं^१ ॥ उदजी-

- 15.—हरच्च बहरीरनाकुलैरभिदश्यशल्यमसिकुंतपट्टिशैः ॥ २७ ॥ कर्णः कोदंडगर्वं वित-
रणमहिमानं च जीमूतवाहः कंदर्पो रूपदर्पं विविधमतिमदं भोजभूशृज्जहातु ॥
ऊर्वासुर्वी यशोभिर्विशदयति शरच्चंद्रगौरैरुदंचदोर्दोडोडंखज्जे प्रभवति बहरीवीरचये
जगत्यां ॥ २८ ॥ चेतस्यंकुरितः प्रमोदपयसा सिक्तः सुपात्रावनादास्त्रा-
16.—नं^२ गमितः सुवर्णमणिभिः पूर्णप्ररोहक्रमः ॥ शाखाभित्तुरगैः पचेलिमफलः
कीर्त्यावदातश्रिया चित्रं दानमहीरुहोस्य बहरीवीरस्य संवर्द्धते ॥ २९ ॥ न कदा-
चिदस्य मदनः पुरस्फुरत्परसुंदरीषु हृदयं व्यचीकरत् ॥ न च लोभवैभवमिमं
व्यमूमुहत् परवस्तुनि स्तुतिपदेपि कुत्रचित् ॥ ३० ॥ अचीखनदुग्धपयोधिशैशवश्रियं
वहत् शाल्मलिमत्पुरे^३-
17.—सरः ॥ अचीकरत्पुण्यमिवात्मनः स्थिरं महत्तरं सेतुमसौ शकाग्रणीः ॥ ३१ ॥
बहरी सरः परममुत्र सुंदरं समचीखनद्धनददिक्समाश्रितं ॥ यदुपेतसोदरसमाग-
मागतो दधिवारिधिः किमयमित्यतकथेत ॥ ३२ ॥ बहरीविनिमितसरःपरिस्फुरत्तरुणा-
रुणारुणसरोजराजिषु ॥ परिहाय भूरिपरिरंभणं हरेरुरसो रमारमत रागवत्तया
॥ ३३ ॥ यत्रो-
18.—लमत्कमलमंडललोलभृंगीसंगीतसंवलितरंगरथांगनादाः ॥ मानेंगनाः पतिपु
मन्मथधाविधाटी घंटारवा इव नयति समुत्सुकत्वं ॥ ३४ ॥ तत्तीरे तरवो रसालपन-
साः पांथव्रजेभ्योनिशं मंत्रं पुष्पफलैरलं व्यतिसृजंत्यामोदिभिः स्वादुभिः ॥ स्पर्द्ध-
ते जनकं तु तद्भुवमर्मा सर्वाभ्रदं सूनवस्तातं स्वं व्यतिशेरते गुणगणैः पुण्यात्मनां
ध्यन्न-
19.—ताः ॥ ३५ ॥ बहरीरकारयत् दीर्घदीर्घिकां ककुभं खिडावदपुरस्य दक्षिणां ॥ अधि-
नद्धनिमंलशिलातले स्फुरद्रचनानमनोज्ञमणिबंधभासुरां ॥ ३६ ॥ पीयूषपोषमविशेष-
मदोषमाप्य वापी पुषोष कतमन्न विशेषमेषा ॥ कालेपि मानससरोवरमाश्रयति
यस्यां निवद्धमनसा न हि मल्लिकाक्षाः ॥ ३७ ॥ या चंद्रकांतपरिकल्पितमिन्तिजातजां-
20.—वनदांबुजततिप्रतिबिंबकांत्या ॥ तीरेपि नीरभरविभ्रमभांजि पांथयूथानि हंत
हसतीव तरंगरंगैः ॥ ३८ ॥ यत्रारहदृष्टितोरुघटीनटीवन्नानट्टिकुट्टिम इव प्रचल-
ज्जलोधे ॥ रज्जौ क्वचित्क्वचन नीरधरांतराले ताले मिलत्युपरिदारुबियोग-
योगैः ॥ ३९ ॥ यत्सोपानश्रेणिरणेक्षणानामंभःकुंभैर्नैतुमभ्युचतानां ॥ फुलांभो-

^१ Read 'स्थिरीभव'.

^२ Read 'स्थानं'.

^३ Read 'बहच्छाल्मलि'.

- 21.—जैर्मजुसिजानहंसैरंशिन्यासैरंचितेवाविभाति¹ ॥ ४० ॥ यक्षीराहरणोपनञ्जतरुणी
कुंभं जले दोलयन्त्याभीयं परिचिन्वती गुरुकुचद्वंद्वानुविबदयं ॥ नो गृह्णाति घटं
न गच्छति तटं वाटं न बावेक्षते संपन्नभ्रमविभ्रमा त्रिकलशोभेवेक्षते विस्मिता ॥ ४१ ॥
नीरक्रीडासंगतैर्यत्र कांता वेणित्राणाबद्धचंडातकांताः ॥ वीचीदोलालोलनीवीमि-
वेशाः स्त्रि-
- 22.—गैरंगीचक्रिरे² वारवध्वः ॥ ४२ ॥ अनर्घ्यतरदीधिकातरणसंमिलत्कामिनीकुचस्थ-
लपरिस्खलनमृगमदैकपंकाविले ॥ सुपंशलशिलयतले कमलमंडलीमंतिकेष्यपास्य
परिविभ्रति भ्रमणमत्र भृंगस्रजः ॥ ४३ ॥ उत्तुंगस्तनभारलंगुरुगुरुश्रोणाभ्रमव्याकुला
यक्षीराहरणाध्वनीनतरुणी विश्रांतिमृच्छेदिति ॥ छायाभूरुहराजिमत्र बहरी-
- 23.—वीरो मुदा वावपद्यामुदञ्जति³ न कुत्रचिन्नवनवोलासावतंसश्रियः । ४४ ॥
उपर्युपरि दीर्घिकां समतले धरामडले मनोहरतरुश्रिया तरणितापलोपेन्नतां ॥
दलःकुसुमसौरभ्रमदभंगभृंगावलीमिलन्मृदुलकाकलीमकृत सोत्र वाटी विभुः ॥
॥ ४५ ॥ श्रोणीभारचलद्रसालवितपव्यालंबिदोलामिलद्वामोरूचलचोलिकांचलचल-
द्रातैरपेत-
- 24.—श्रमः ॥ जेतुं पंचशरः शरानिव जगद्भू[या] जितं विभ्रमानिभ्यो लंभ-
यति स्म सैनिकाधिया मन्येत्र लीलावने ॥ ४६ ॥ पनसे पचेलिमफले चलदृशा
कतभेन नास्मृत्यत⁴ यत्र कानने ॥ परिरंभसंभ्रमदलत्तनूरुहा विरहे प्रियापृथुप-
योधरद्वयी ॥ ४७ ॥ स्पर्धते लकुचफलानि बालिकानामुद्भिन्नस्तयुगलेन⁵ कानने-
स्मिन् ॥ कुंदानामाविकलकोर-
- 25.—कस्रजोपि व्याकोशाधरपुटीवम्फुरत्प्रमितेन ॥ ४८ ॥ आश्रेयं कुसुमितमालतीलताना-
मासाद्यामलजलर्दाधिकामिषिक्तः ॥ स्वदांभोनिवहमलुंपदंगनानामश्रांतं श्रमजमसुत्र
गंधवाहः ॥ ४९ ॥ इदं कचन काननं मृदुलमल्लिकाशोभनं कचित्कनककेतकप्रकरभू-
रिवानीरवत् ॥ कचिन्मधुरसारसर्गाहलकोकिलविभ्रमं कचिन्वत्तृणपल्लवैरुगणितांतराल-
द्रुमं ॥ ५० ॥
- 26.—वनं कापि पुन्नागरगावरुद्धं⁶ कचिन्तुंगनारंगभंगावनद्धं ॥ कचिन्चंपकरवच्छगुच्छप्रपंचं
कचिन्तुंगसंरब्धसंगीतसंचं ॥ ५१ ॥ कचिन्चिन्तमुत्कंठते मंजुगंधे मनो मोदते कुत्रचित्कुं-
जबंधे ॥ इहाहंयुजा या जहाति प्रकोपं प्रिये नानुरागस्य धत्ते विलोपं ॥ ५२ ॥
कचिन्सारणीवारिपूरा बलात कचिन्मालतीपुष्पमाला दलंति ॥ कचिन्कोकिला मंजु
सज्जति गा-

¹ Read ° रंभि. °

² Read उज्झन्ति.

³ Read ° स्तनयुगलेन.

⁴ Read क्षिप्ति.

⁵ Read नास्मर्यत.

⁶ Read पुन्नागं.

27.—नं कचिचोषितस्तेन मुंचति [मानं] ॥ ५३ ॥ कचिन्नालिकेरीतरुश्रेणिसंपन्निकुं-
जीभवद्यथिकावल्लिसंसव ॥ मिलन्मातुलिगद्रुमद्रोणियुक्ते वने राजते पारसीकप्र-
युक्ते ॥ ५४ ॥ विटपानुपंगकृतकंटकव्यथां शतपत्रचित्रकुसुमावचायिकां ॥ विजनेपि
मालिकयुवात्र कानने विगतागसं न रमणीममन्यत ॥ ५५ ॥ यावत्शेषशिरस्सु^१
भूमिवलयं भूमंड-

28.—ले मध्यतो मेरुमैरुगिरावसावहरहः प्रद्योतते भास्करः ॥ तावद्वापिकया सहेह
बहरी सत्पुत्रपौत्रावृतो निःप्रत्यूहमचंचलप्रमुदितश्रीसंश्रितो नंदतु ॥ ५६ ॥ बंशे
भृगोभैगवतो भुवनप्रकाशे चंद्रावतंसचरणबुजचंचरीकः ॥ आसीत्पवित्रचारितोनु-
वसंतयाजी श्रीसोमनाथधरणीविवुधो धरण्यां ॥ ५७ ॥ तस्यात्मजो नरहरिर्हरिरेव
साक्षादान्वा-

29.—क्षिकीकुमुदकाननशांतभानुः ॥ आसीदिलालविरंचिरिति स्फुटार्थ यो वेद वेद-
वसतिर्बिरुदं बभार ॥ ५८ ॥ तस्मादंबुजिनीपतेरिव मनुश्रंङ्घ्यतिः कश्यपादंभोजास-
नतो भृगुजंलनिधेर्यद्रसुधादीधितिः ॥ संजातो नृहरेरहीनमहिमा श्रीकेशवः कीर्त्ति-
मान् यो झोटिंग इति प्रथामुदवहदुर्वादिपंचाननः ॥ ५९ ॥ अत्रिस्तत्तनयो नयकनि-

30.—लयो वेदांतदांतरिथतिर्मांसारसमांसलतुलमतिः साहित्यसौहित्यवान् ॥ मान्यः
श्रीगुहिलान्वयांबुजवतीविद्योतनस्याभवत्श्रीमत्कुंभमहीपतेर्द्देशपुरज्ञातिद्विजाग्नेसरः^२
॥ ६० ॥ अत्रेः सूनुर्दशनांभोजभानुर्वाद्दश्रेणीवाक्यवह्नीकृशानुः ॥ किं-
चित्कालं मालवेराजतोषत्काव्योह्लासेः श्रीमहेशः कवीद्रः ॥ ६१ ॥ बहरीविनिर्भि-

31.—तमुर्दाघदीधिकामधि स प्रशस्तिकरोन्महेश्वरः ॥ अनवद्यपद्यविकसद्रसिश्रिया
परितापितोत्तमकवीद्रमानसः ॥ ६२ ॥ श्रीमद्विक्रमभूमिभर्तृसमयाच्चंद्रागमेध्विदुभि-
विख्याते परिधावित्सरवरे मासे लसत्कार्तिके ॥ शुद्धे धर्मतिथौ बृहस्पतियुते^३
पूर्णाभवद्दीधिका दीर्घायुर्बहरी बहूनि वितरन् वित्तानि यामातनोव ॥ ६३ ॥
मध्ये सितासि-

32.—तसरिद्धितयं चकारस्ति पूः पावनश्रुतिहमीरपुराभिधाना ॥ तस्यां बभूव^४ करचु-
ल्लिकुलांशुमाली श्रीभैरवो नृपतिरुग्रतरप्रतापः ॥ ६४ ॥ श्रीभैरवावनिपतेरभवत्सु-
मेधा माध्यंदिनद्विजवरः कुशलद्विवेदः ॥ तत्सूनुरर्धपतिरुच्चतरं चकार गोत्रं
गुणैरनणु भार्गवनामधेयं ॥ ६५ ॥ तत्सूनुः पुरुषोत्तमखिनयनं भक्त्या समाराधयन्
वेदव्याकृतिसंप्रदायप-

^१ Read यावच्छेषः

^२ Read बृहस्पतिः

^३ Read भवच्छ्रीः

^४ Read बभूव.

33. —रमाचार्यो बभूवावनौ ॥ तत्पुत्रो घुडऊ कलासु कुशलो मान्योस्ति भूमिभुजामेनं
कादिरसाहिभूपतिरनैषीत् पारसीकस्थितिं ॥६६॥ यवनत्वमाप्य घुडऊ गुणांशुभिः
प्रभुतावशेन शलहामिधामधात् ॥ अमणच्च खानममुमुप्रतेजसं महमूदभूपतिरनल्प-
विक्रमः ॥६७॥ शलहो यवनमकार्षीद्दहरीवीरं च बाहुजं जाल्या ॥ पत्नौ वर्णिता
पूर्वौ महे-
34. —शकविना प्रसंगसंगत्या ॥६८॥ झांझासुनुर्दाधिकं क्षेत्रसिद्धः शस्ताकारां सूत्रधारो
व्यधत् ॥ शिल्पं यस्यावेक्ष्य कश्चिन्न शिल्पी शिल्पे गर्वग्रथिमुर्व्या विभर्ति ॥ ६९॥
शुभं भवतु लेखकपाठकयोः ॥ शुभं ॥ ७ ॥